

NEW CONGRUENCES FOR OVERPARTITIONS INTO ODD PARTS

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Abstract

Let $\bar{p}_o(n)$ denote the number of overpartitions of n into odd parts. In this article, we study congruences for $\bar{p}_o(n)$ modulo 8 and 16. Chen proved that $\bar{p}_o(n)$ satisfies the identity

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(16n+14)q^n = 112 \frac{f_2^{27}}{f_1^{25} f_4^2} + 256q \frac{f_2^3 f_4^{14}}{f_1^{17}},$$

where $f_k := \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^{nk})$. We prove similar identities for $\bar{p}_o(16n+2)$, $\bar{p}_o(16n+6)$, and $\bar{p}_o(16n+10)$. Along the way, we find a new proof of the identity of Chen. We also derive infinite families of congruences modulo 8 and 16 for $\bar{p}_o(n)$. We use Ramanujan's theta function identities and some new p -dissections in our proofs.

1. Introduction and Statement of Results

Throughout this paper, for complex numbers a and q , $(a; q)_{\infty}$ stands for the q -shifted factorial

$$(a; q)_{\infty} = \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} (1 - aq^{n-1}), \quad |q| < 1; \quad (1)$$

and f_k stands for $(q^k; q^k)_{\infty}$. In [7], Corteel and Lovejoy introduce the notion of overpartitions. Many interesting arithmetic properties of overpartitions are found

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by many mathematicians, for example, see Mahlburg [14], Hirschhorn and Sellers [10], and Kim [12, 13]. An *overpartition* of a nonnegative integer n is a partition of n in which the first occurrence of a part may be over-lined. For example, the eight overpartitions of 3 are $3, \overline{3}, 2 + 1, \overline{2} + 1, 2 + \overline{1}, \overline{2} + \overline{1}, 1 + 1 + 1$, and $\overline{1} + 1 + 1$. Let $\overline{p}(n)$ denote the number of overpartitions of n . The generating function for $\overline{p}(n)$ is given by

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \overline{p}(n)q^n = \frac{(-q; q)_{\infty}}{(q; q)_{\infty}} = \frac{f_2}{f_1^2}. \tag{2}$$

For $|ab| < 1$, Ramanujan’s general theta function $f(a, b)$ is defined as

$$f(a, b) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} a^{n(n+1)/2} b^{n(n-1)/2}. \tag{3}$$

In Ramanujan’s notation, the Jacobi triple product identity [4, Entry 19, p. 36] takes the shape

$$f(a, b) = (-a; ab)_{\infty} (-b; ab)_{\infty} (ab; ab)_{\infty}. \tag{4}$$

The most important special cases of $f(a, b)$ are

$$\varphi(q) := f(q, q) = 1 + 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} q^{n^2} = \frac{f_2^5}{f_1^2 f_4^2}, \tag{5}$$

$$\psi(q) := f(q, q^3) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} q^{n(n+1)/2} = \frac{f_2^2}{f_1}, \tag{6}$$

$$f(-q) := f(-q, -q^2) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} (-1)^n q^{n(3n-1)/2} = f_1. \tag{7}$$

We now recall two definitions from [9, p. 225]. Let Π represent a pentagonal number (a number of the form $\frac{3n^2+n}{2}$) and Ω represent an octagonal number (a number of the form $3n^2 + 2n$). Let $\Pi(q) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} q^{\frac{3n^2+n}{2}}$ and $\Omega(q) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} q^{3n^2+2n}$. Then,

$$\Pi(q) = \frac{f_2 f_3^2}{f_1 f_6}. \tag{8}$$

Also,

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega(-q) &= \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} (-1)^n q^{3n^2+2n} = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} (-1)^n q^{3n^2-2n} \\ &= \prod_{n \geq 1} (1 - q^{6n-5})(1 - q^{6n-1})(1 - q^{6n}) = \frac{f_1 f_6^2}{f_2 f_3}. \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

In this article, we study overpartitions in which only odd parts are used. This function has arisen in a number of recent papers, but in contexts which are very different from overpartitions. For example, see Ardonne, Kedem and Stone [1], Bessenrodt [3], and Santos and Sills [15]. We denote by $\bar{p}_o(n)$ the number of overpartitions of n into odd parts. Hirschhorn and Sellers [11] obtain many interesting arithmetic properties of $\bar{p}_o(n)$. They observe that the generating function for $\bar{p}_o(n)$ is given by

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(n)q^n = \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1 + q^{2n-1}}{1 - q^{2n-1}} = \frac{f_2^3}{f_1^2 f_4}. \tag{10}$$

They establish a number of arithmetic results including several Ramanujan-like congruences satisfied by $\bar{p}_o(n)$, and some easily-stated characterizations of $\bar{p}_o(n)$ modulo small powers of 2. For example, the following two Ramanujan-like congruences can readily be seen from one of their main theorems:

$$\bar{p}_o(8n + 5) \equiv 0 \pmod{8}, \tag{11}$$

$$\bar{p}_o(8n + 7) \equiv 0 \pmod{16}. \tag{12}$$

They also prove that, for $n \geq 1$, $\bar{p}_o(n)$ is divisible by 4 if and only if n is neither a square nor twice a square. In [6, Theorem 1], Chen proves that

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(16n + 14)q^n = 112 \frac{f_2^{27}}{f_1^{25} f_4^2} + 256q \frac{f_2^3 f_4^{14}}{f_1^{17}}, \tag{13}$$

from which it readily follows that $\bar{p}_o(16n + 14) \equiv 0 \pmod{16}$. Using elementary theory of modular forms, he further proves infinitely many congruences for $\bar{p}_o(n)$ modulo 32 and 64. Let $t \geq 0$ be an integer and $p_1, p_2 \equiv 1 \pmod{8}$ be primes. Chen [6, Theorem 2] proves that

$$\bar{p}_o(p_1^{2t+1}(16n + 14)) \equiv 0 \pmod{32}, \tag{14}$$

$$\bar{p}_o(p_1^{4t+3}(16n + 14)) \equiv 0 \pmod{64}, \tag{15}$$

$$\bar{p}_o(p_1 p_2(16n + 14)) \equiv 0 \pmod{64}. \tag{16}$$

The first two congruences are valid for all nonnegative integers n satisfying $8n \not\equiv -7 \pmod{p_1}$. The last congruence is valid for all nonnegative integers n satisfying $8n \not\equiv -7 \pmod{p_1}$ and $8n \not\equiv -7 \pmod{p_2}$.

In this article, we prove the following identities for $\bar{p}_o(n)$ similar to (13) for other values of n . Along the way, we also obtain (13).

Theorem 1. *We have*

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(4n)q^n = \frac{f_2^5 f_4^3}{f_1^6 f_8^2}, \tag{17}$$

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(4n+1)q^n = 2 \frac{f_4^7}{f_1^4 f_2 f_8^2}, \tag{18}$$

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(4n+2)q^n = 2 \frac{f_2^7 f_8^2}{f_1^6 f_4^3}, \tag{19}$$

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(4n+3)q^n = 4 \frac{f_2 f_4 f_8^2}{f_1^4}, \tag{20}$$

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(16n+2)q^n = 2 \frac{f_2^{45}}{f_1^{31} f_4^{14}} + 224q \frac{f_2^{21} f_4^2}{f_1^{23}}, \tag{21}$$

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(16n+6)q^n = 12 \frac{f_2^{39}}{f_1^{29} f_4^{10}} + 320q \frac{f_2^{15} f_4^6}{f_1^{21}}, \tag{22}$$

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(16n+10)q^n = 40 \frac{f_2^{33}}{f_1^{27} f_4^6} + 384q \frac{f_2^9 f_4^{10}}{f_1^{19}}. \tag{23}$$

We also find congruences modulo 8 and 16 for $\bar{p}_o(n)$ using Ramanujan’s theta function identities and some dissections of theta functions. We prove the following congruences for $\bar{p}_o(n)$ modulo 8 and 16.

Theorem 2. *We have*

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(8n+3)q^n \equiv 4 \frac{f_2^5}{f_1} \pmod{16}, \tag{24}$$

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(16n+6)q^n \equiv 12 \frac{f_2^5}{f_1} \pmod{16}, \tag{25}$$

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(16n+10)q^n \equiv 8 \frac{f_2^2 f_4^3}{f_1} \pmod{16}, \tag{26}$$

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(32n+4)q^n \equiv 6 \frac{f_1 f_2^5}{f_4^2} \pmod{8}, \tag{27}$$

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(32n+12)q^n \equiv 4 \frac{f_1^3 f_4^2}{f_2} \pmod{8}, \tag{28}$$

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(24n+1)q^n \equiv 2 \frac{f_2}{f_1} \pmod{8}, \tag{29}$$

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(24n+17)q^n \equiv 4 \frac{f_1 f_3^2 f_6^2}{f_2} \pmod{8}, \tag{30}$$

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(72n+9)q^n \equiv 6 f_1 f_2 \pmod{8}. \tag{31}$$

Theorem 3. For nonnegative integers n and α we have

$$\bar{p}_o(2^\alpha(32n + 20)) \equiv 0 \pmod{8}, \tag{32}$$

$$\bar{p}_o(2^\alpha(32n + 28)) \equiv 0 \pmod{8}. \tag{33}$$

We next prove certain infinite families of congruences for $\bar{p}_o(n)$ modulo 8 and 16 as stated in the following theorems. We establish new p -dissections of $\frac{f_2^5}{f_4^2}$ and $\Omega(-q)$, and use them to prove the congruences.

We recall that, for an odd prime p , the Legendre symbol is defined by

$$\left(\frac{a}{p}\right) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } a \text{ is a square modulo } p \text{ and } a \not\equiv 0 \pmod{p}; \\ -1 & \text{if } a \text{ is not a square modulo } p; \\ 0 & \text{if } a \equiv 0 \pmod{p}. \end{cases}$$

Theorem 4. Let $p \geq 3$ be a prime, $n \geq 0$ and $\alpha \geq 1$. If $\left(\frac{-2}{p}\right) = -1$, then we have

$$\bar{p}_o(8p^{2\alpha}n + (3p + 8j)p^{2\alpha-1}) \equiv 0 \pmod{16}, \tag{34}$$

$$\bar{p}_o(16p^{2\alpha}n + (6p + 16j)p^{2\alpha-1}) \equiv 0 \pmod{16}, \tag{35}$$

$$\bar{p}_o(72p^{2\alpha}n + (9p + 72j)p^{2\alpha-1}) \equiv 0 \pmod{8}, \tag{36}$$

$$\bar{p}_o(24p^{2\alpha}n + (17p + 24j)p^{2\alpha-1}) \equiv 0 \pmod{8}, \tag{37}$$

$$\bar{p}_o(32p^{2\alpha}n + (4p + 32j)p^{2\alpha-1}) \equiv 0 \pmod{8}, \tag{38}$$

$$\bar{p}_o(32p^{2\alpha}n + (12p + 32j)p^{2\alpha-1}) \equiv 0 \pmod{8}. \tag{39}$$

If $p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$, then we have

$$\bar{p}_o(16p^{2\alpha}n + (10p + 16j)p^{2\alpha-1}) \equiv 0 \pmod{16}, \tag{40}$$

where $j = 1, 2, \dots, p - 1$.

2. Preliminaries

In this section, we study certain p -dissection identities. We first state the following 4-dissection formula from [9, (1.9.4)] and [4, Entry 25, p. 40].

Lemma 1. We have

$$\varphi(q) = \varphi(q^4) + 2q\psi(q^8). \tag{41}$$

That is,

$$\frac{1}{f_1^2} = \frac{f_8^5}{f_2^5 f_{16}^2} + 2q \frac{f_4^2 f_{16}^2}{f_2^5 f_8}. \tag{42}$$

We next recall the following 3-dissection formula from [9, (26.1.2)] and [4, Corollary (i), p. 49].

Lemma 2. *We have*

$$\psi(q) = \Pi(q^3) + 2q\psi(q^9). \tag{43}$$

That is,

$$\frac{f_2^2}{f_1} = \frac{f_6 f_9^2}{f_3 f_{18}} + q \frac{f_{18}^2}{f_9}. \tag{44}$$

The following 4-dissection formulas are due to Hirschhorn and Sellers [10].

Lemma 3. *We have*

$$\frac{1}{\varphi(-q)} = \frac{1}{\varphi(-q^4)^4} (\varphi(q^4)^3 + 2q\varphi(q^4)^2\psi(q^8) + 4q^2\varphi(q^4)\psi(q^8)^2 + 8q^3\psi(q^8)^3). \tag{45}$$

That is,

$$\frac{f_2}{f_1^2} = \frac{f_8^4}{f_4^8} \left(\frac{f_8^{15}}{f_4^6 f_{16}^6} + 2q \frac{f_8^9}{f_4^4 f_{16}^2} + 4q^2 \frac{f_8^3 f_{16}^2}{f_4^2} + 8q^3 \frac{f_{16}^6}{f_8^3} \right). \tag{46}$$

The following 3-dissection formulas are due to Hirschhorn and Sellers [10].

Lemma 4. *We have*

$$\frac{1}{\varphi(-q)} = \frac{\varphi(-q^9)}{\varphi(-q^3)^4} (\varphi(-q^9)^2 + 2q\varphi(-q^9)\Omega(-q^3) + 4q^2\Omega(-q^3)^2). \tag{47}$$

That is,

$$\frac{f_2}{f_1^2} = \frac{f_6^4 f_9^2}{f_3^8 f_{18}} \left(\frac{f_9^4}{f_{18}^2} + 2q \frac{f_3 f_9 f_{18}}{f_6} + 4q^2 \frac{f_3^2 f_{18}^4}{f_6^2 f_9^2} \right). \tag{48}$$

We now recall p -dissections of $\psi(q)$, $f(-q)$ and $\psi(q^2)f(-q)^2$ which will be used to prove our main results.

Lemma 5. [8, Theorem 2.1] *For any odd prime p , we have*

$$\psi(q) = \sum_{k=0}^{\frac{p-3}{2}} q^{\frac{k^2+k}{2}} f \left(q^{\frac{p^2+(2k+1)p}{2}}, q^{\frac{p^2-(2k+1)p}{2}} \right) + q^{\frac{p^2-1}{8}} \psi(q^{p^2}). \tag{49}$$

Furthermore, for $0 \leq k \leq \frac{p-3}{2}$, $\frac{k^2+k}{2} \not\equiv \frac{p^2-1}{8} \pmod{p}$.

Before we state the next lemma, we define that for any prime $p \geq 5$,

$$\frac{\pm p - 1}{6} := \begin{cases} \frac{p-1}{6} & \text{if } p \equiv 1 \pmod{6}; \\ \frac{-p-1}{6} & \text{if } p \equiv -1 \pmod{6}. \end{cases}$$

Lemma 6. [8, Theorem 2.2] For any prime $p \geq 5$, we have

$$f(-q) = \sum_{\substack{k=-\frac{p-1}{2} \\ k \neq \frac{\pm p-1}{6}}}^{\frac{p-1}{2}} (-1)^k q^{\frac{3k^2+k}{2}} f\left(-q^{\frac{3p^2+(6k+1)p}{2}}, -q^{\frac{3p^2-(6k+1)p}{2}}\right) + (-1)^{\frac{\pm p-1}{6}} q^{\frac{p^2-1}{24}} f(-q^{p^2}). \tag{50}$$

Furthermore, if $-\frac{p-1}{2} \leq k \leq \frac{p-1}{2}$ and $k \neq \frac{\pm p-1}{6}$, then $\frac{3k^2+k}{2} \not\equiv \frac{p^2-1}{24} \pmod{p}$.

Lemma 7. [2, Lemma 2.4] If $p \geq 5$ is a prime and

$$\frac{\pm p-1}{3} := \begin{cases} \frac{p-1}{3} & \text{if } p \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \\ -\frac{p-1}{3} & \text{if } p \equiv -1 \pmod{3}, \end{cases}$$

then

$$\psi(q^2)f(-q)^2 = \sum_{\substack{k=-\frac{p-1}{2} \\ k \neq \frac{\pm p-1}{3}}}^{\frac{p-1}{2}} q^{3k^2+2k} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} (3pn+3k+1)q^{pn(3pn+6k+2)} \pm pq^{\frac{p^2-1}{3}} \psi(q^{2p^2})f(-q^{p^2})^2. \tag{51}$$

Furthermore, if $k \neq \frac{\pm p-1}{3}$ and $-\frac{p-1}{2} \leq k \leq \frac{p-1}{2}$, then $3k^2+2k \not\equiv \frac{p^2-1}{3} \pmod{p}$.

The following lemma readily follows from [2, Lemma 2.3] by putting q^2 in place of q . The lemma gives a p -dissection of $f(-q^2)^3$.

Lemma 8. For any prime $p \geq 3$, we have

$$f(-q^2)^3 = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\substack{k=0 \\ k \neq \frac{p-1}{2}}}^{p-1} (-1)^k q^{k^2+k} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} (-1)^n (2pn+2k+1)q^{pn(pn+2k+1)} + (-1)^{\frac{p-1}{2}} pq^{\frac{p^2-1}{4}} f(-q^{2p^2})^3. \tag{52}$$

Furthermore, if $0 \leq k \leq p-1$ and $k \neq \frac{p-1}{2}$, then $k^2+k \not\equiv \frac{p^2-1}{4} \pmod{p}$.

In the following two lemmas, we deduce new p -dissections of $\frac{f_2^5}{f_4}$ and $\Omega(-q)$, respectively.

Lemma 9. For a prime $p \geq 5$,

$$\frac{f_2^5}{f_4} = \sum_{\substack{k=-\frac{p-1}{2} \\ k \neq \frac{\pm p-1}{6}}}^{\frac{p-1}{2}} q^{3k^2+k} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} (6pn+6k+1)q^{pn(3pn+6k+1)} \pm pq^{\frac{p^2-1}{12}} \frac{f_{2p^2}^5}{f_{4p^2}^2}. \tag{53}$$

In addition, if $-\frac{p-1}{2} \leq k \leq \frac{p-1}{2}$ and $k \neq \frac{\pm p-1}{6}$, then $3k^2+k \not\equiv \frac{p^2-1}{12} \pmod{p}$.

Proof. Due to Hirschhorn [9, (10.7.3)] and Berndt [5, (1.3.60)], we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{f_2^5}{f_4^2} &= \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} (6n+1)q^{3n^2+n} \\
 &= \sum_{k=-\frac{p-1}{2}}^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} [6(pn+k)+1]q^{3(pn+k)^2+(pn+k)} \\
 &= \sum_{k=-\frac{p-1}{2}}^{\frac{p-1}{2}} q^{3k^2+k} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} (6pn+6k+1)q^{pn(3pn+6k+1)} \\
 &= \sum_{\substack{k=-\frac{p-1}{2} \\ k \neq \pm\frac{p-1}{6}}}^{\frac{p-1}{2}} q^{3k^2+k} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} (6pn+6k+1)q^{pn(3pn+6k+1)} \\
 &\quad \pm q^{\frac{p^2-1}{12}} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} p(6n+1)q^{p^2(3n^2+n)} \\
 &= \sum_{\substack{k=-\frac{p-1}{2} \\ k \neq \pm\frac{p-1}{6}}}^{\frac{p-1}{2}} q^{3k^2+k} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} (6pn+6k+1)q^{pn(3pn+6k+1)} \pm pq^{\frac{p^2-1}{12}} \frac{f_2^5}{f_4^2}.
 \end{aligned}$$

We observe that, for $-\frac{p-1}{2} \leq k \leq \frac{p-1}{2}$, if $3k^2+k \equiv \frac{p^2-1}{12} \pmod{p}$, then we have $(6k+1)^2 \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$, which yields $k = \pm\frac{p-1}{6}$. $\square$

Lemma 10. *If $p \geq 5$ is a prime and*

$$\frac{\pm p+1}{3} := \begin{cases} \frac{-p+1}{3} & \text{if } p \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \\ \frac{p+1}{3} & \text{if } p \equiv -1 \pmod{3}, \end{cases}$$

then

$$\Omega(-q) = \sum_{\substack{k=-\frac{p-1}{2} \\ k \neq \pm\frac{p+1}{3}}}^{\frac{p-1}{2}} (-1)^k q^{3k^2-2k} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} (-1)^n q^{pn(3pn+6k-2)} + (-1)^{\frac{\pm p+1}{3}} q^{\frac{p^2-1}{3}} \Omega(-q^{p^2}). \tag{54}$$

Furthermore, if $-\frac{p-1}{2} \leq k \leq \frac{p-1}{2}$ and $k \neq \pm\frac{p+1}{3}$, then $3k^2-2k \not\equiv \frac{p^2-1}{3} \pmod{p}$.

Proof. From (9), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Omega(-q) &= \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} (-1)^n q^{3n^2-2n} \\
 &= \sum_{k=-\frac{p-1}{2}}^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} (-1)^{pn+k} q^{3(pn+k)^2-2(pn+k)} \\
 &= \sum_{k=-\frac{p-1}{2}}^{\frac{p-1}{2}} (-1)^k q^{3k^2-2k} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} (-1)^n q^{pn(3pn+6k-2)} \\
 &= \sum_{\substack{k=-\frac{p-1}{2} \\ k \neq \frac{\pm p+1}{3}}}^{\frac{p-1}{2}} (-1)^k q^{3k^2-2k} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} (-1)^n q^{pn(3pn+6k-2)} \\
 &\quad + (-1)^{\frac{\pm p+1}{3}} q^{\frac{p^2-1}{3}} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} (-1)^n q^{p^2(3n^2-2n)} \\
 &= \sum_{\substack{k=-\frac{p-1}{2} \\ k \neq \frac{\pm p+1}{3}}}^{\frac{p-1}{2}} (-1)^k q^{3k^2-2k} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} (-1)^n q^{pn(3pn+6k-2)} \\
 &\quad + (-1)^{\frac{\pm p+1}{3}} q^{\frac{p^2-1}{3}} \Omega(-q^{p^2}).
 \end{aligned}$$

Note that, if $3k^2 - 2k \equiv \frac{p^2-1}{3} \pmod{p}$, then $k = \frac{\pm p+1}{3}$. □

3. Proofs of Theorem 1, Theorem 2 and Theorem 3

In this section, we prove Theorems 1, 2 and 3.

Proof of Theorem 1. From (10) and (41), we find that

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(n) q^n = \frac{f_2^3}{f_1^2 f_4} \tag{55}$$

$$= \frac{f_2^3}{f_4} \left(\frac{1}{f_1^2} \right) \tag{56}$$

$$= \frac{f_2^3}{f_4} \left(\frac{f_4^2}{f_2^5} \varphi(q) \right) \tag{57}$$

$$= \frac{f_4}{f_2^2} \varphi(q) \tag{58}$$

$$= \frac{\varphi(q)}{\varphi(-q^2)} \tag{59}$$

$$= \frac{\varphi(q)\varphi(q^2)}{\varphi(q^2)\varphi(-q^2)} \tag{60}$$

$$= \frac{\varphi(q)\varphi(q^2)}{\varphi(-q^4)^2} \tag{61}$$

$$= \frac{(\varphi(q^4) + 2q\psi(q^8)) (\varphi(q^8) + 2q^2\psi(q^{16}))}{\varphi(-q^4)^2}, \tag{62}$$

from which it follows that

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(4n)q^n = \frac{\varphi(q)\varphi(q^2)}{\varphi(-q)^2} = \frac{f_2^5}{f_1^2 f_4^2} \frac{f_4^5}{f_2^2 f_8^2} \frac{f_2^2}{f_1^4} = \frac{f_2^5 f_4^3}{f_1^6 f_8^2}, \tag{63}$$

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(4n+1)q^n = 2 \frac{\psi(q^2)\varphi(q^2)}{\varphi(-q)^2} = 2 \frac{f_4^2}{f_2} \frac{f_4^5}{f_2^2 f_8^2} \frac{f_2^2}{f_1^4} = 2 \frac{f_4^7}{f_1^4 f_2 f_8^2}, \tag{64}$$

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(4n+2)q^n = 2 \frac{\varphi(q)\psi(q^4)}{\varphi(-q)^2} = 2 \frac{f_2^5}{f_1^2 f_4^2} \frac{f_8^2}{f_4} \frac{f_2^2}{f_1^4} = 2 \frac{f_2^7 f_8^2}{f_1^6 f_4^3}, \tag{65}$$

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(4n+3)q^n = 4 \frac{\psi(q^2)\psi(q^4)}{\varphi(-q)^2} = 4 \frac{f_4^2}{f_2} \frac{f_8^2}{f_4} \frac{f_2^2}{f_1^4} = 4 \frac{f_2 f_4 f_8^2}{f_1^4}. \tag{66}$$

This completes the proofs of (17), (18), (19) and (20). We note that the identity (20) is also found by Hirschhorn and Sellers [10, Theorem 2.12].

Using (41) and (45) in (19), we deduce that

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(4n+2)q^n \tag{67}$$

$$= 2 \frac{f_2^7 f_8^2}{f_1^6 f_4^3} \tag{68}$$

$$= 2 \left(\frac{f_8^2}{f_4} \right) \left(\frac{f_2^5}{f_1^2 f_4^2} \right) \left(\frac{f_2^2}{f_1^4} \right) \tag{69}$$

$$= 2\psi(q^4)\varphi(q) \frac{1}{\varphi(-q)^2} \tag{70}$$

$$= 2 \frac{\psi(q^4)}{\varphi(-q^4)^8} (\varphi(q^4) + 2q\psi(q^8)) \tag{71}$$

$$\times (\varphi(q^4)^3 + 2q\varphi(q^4)^2\psi(q^8) + 4q^2\varphi(q^4)\psi(q^8)^2 + 8q^3\psi(q^8)^3)^2$$

$$= 2 \frac{\psi(q^4)}{\varphi(-q^4)^8} (\varphi(q^4) + 2q\psi(q^8)) (\varphi(q^4)^6 + 4q\varphi(q^4)^5\psi(q^8) + 12q^2\varphi(q^4)^4\psi(q^8)^2$$

$$+ 32q^3\varphi(q^4)^3\psi(q^8)^3 + 48q^4\varphi(q^4)^2\psi(q^8)^4 + 64q^5\varphi(q^4)\psi(q^8)^5 + 64q^6\psi(q^8)^6) \tag{72}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= 2 \frac{\psi(q^4)}{\varphi(-q^4)^8} (\varphi(q^4)^7 + 6q\varphi(q^4)^6\psi(q^8) + 20q^2\varphi(q^4)^5\psi(q^8)^2 + 56q^3\varphi(q^4)^4\psi(q^8)^3 \\
 &\hspace{20em} (73) \\
 &+ 112q^4\varphi(q^4)^3\psi(q^8)^4 + 160q^5\varphi(q^4)^2\psi(q^8)^5 + 192q^6\varphi(q^4)\psi(q^8)^6 + 128q^7\psi(q^8)^7).
 \end{aligned}$$

Extracting the terms containing q^{4n+i} for $i = 0, 1, 2$, respectively, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(16n+2)q^n \\
 &= 2 \frac{\varphi(q)^7\psi(q)}{\varphi(-q)^8} + 224q \frac{\varphi(q)^3\psi(q)\psi(q^2)^4}{\varphi(-q)^8} = 2 \frac{f_2^{45}}{f_1^{31}f_4^{14}} + 224q \frac{f_2^{21}f_4^2}{f_1^{23}}, \hspace{2em} (74)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(16n+6)q^n \\
 &= 12 \frac{\varphi(q)^6\psi(q)\psi(q^2)}{\varphi(-q)^8} + 320q \frac{\varphi(q)^2\psi(q)\psi(q^2)^5}{\varphi(-q)^8} = 12 \frac{f_2^{39}}{f_1^{29}f_4^{10}} + 320q \frac{f_2^{15}f_4^6}{f_1^{21}}, \hspace{2em} (75)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(16n+10)q^n \\
 &= 40 \frac{\varphi(q)^5\psi(q)\psi(q^2)^2}{\varphi(-q)^8} + 384q \frac{\varphi(q)\psi(q)\psi(q^2)^6}{\varphi(-q)^8} = 40 \frac{f_2^{33}}{f_1^{27}f_4^6} + 384q \frac{f_2^9f_4^{10}}{f_1^{19}}. \hspace{2em} (76)
 \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proofs of (21), (22) and (23), respectively. □

Remark 1. If we extract the coefficients of q^{4n+3} from (73), we readily obtain (13).

We now prove Theorem 2.

Proof of Theorem 2. From the binomial theorem, we have

$$f_1^4 \equiv f_2^2 \pmod{4}. \hspace{10em} (77)$$

Now, applying the above congruence in (20), we obtain

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(4n+3)q^n = 4 \frac{f_2f_4f_8^2}{f_1^4} \hspace{10em} (78)$$

$$= 4 \left(\frac{f_2}{f_1^4} \right) (f_4f_8^2) \hspace{10em} (79)$$

$$\equiv 4 \left(\frac{f_2}{f_2^2} \right) (f_4f_4^4) \hspace{10em} (80)$$

$$= 4 \frac{f_4^5}{f_2} \pmod{16}. \hspace{10em} (81)$$

Extracting the terms containing q^{2n} , we readily deduce (24).

Using the binomial theorem, from (22) and (23), we obtain, respectively, modulo 16,

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(16n + 6)q^n \equiv 12 \frac{f_2^{39}}{f_1^{29} f_4^{10}} = 12 \left(\frac{f_2^{14}}{f_1^{28}} \right) \frac{f_2^5}{f_1} \left(\frac{f_2^{20}}{f_4^{10}} \right) \equiv 12 \frac{f_2^5}{f_1}, \tag{82}$$

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(16n + 10)q^n \equiv 8 \frac{f_2^{33}}{f_1^{27} f_4^6} = 8 \left(\frac{f_2^{13}}{f_1^{26}} \right) \frac{f_2^2 f_4^3}{f_1} \left(\frac{f_2^{18}}{f_4^9} \right) \equiv 8 \frac{f_2^2 f_4^3}{f_1}. \tag{83}$$

This completes the proofs of (25) and (26).

From (17) and (41), we obtain

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(4n)q^n = \frac{f_2^5 f_4^3}{f_1^6 f_8^2} \tag{84}$$

$$= \frac{f_2^5 f_4^3}{f_8^2} \left(\frac{1}{f_1^2} \right)^3 \tag{85}$$

$$= \frac{f_2^5 f_4^3}{f_8^2} \left(\frac{f_4^2}{f_2^5} \varphi(q) \right)^3 \tag{86}$$

$$= \frac{f_4^9}{f_2^{10} f_8^2} \varphi(q)^3 \tag{87}$$

$$= \frac{f_4^9}{f_2^{10} f_8^2} (\varphi(q^4) + 2q\psi(q^8))^3 \tag{88}$$

$$= \frac{f_4^9}{f_2^{10} f_8^2} (\varphi(q^4)^3 + 6q\varphi(q^4)^2\psi(q^8) + 12q^2\varphi(q^4)\psi(q^8)^2 + 8q^3\psi(q^8)^3). \tag{89}$$

Extracting the terms containing q^{2n+1} , and then using the binomial theorem, we obtain, modulo 8,

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(8n + 4)q^n = \frac{f_2^9}{f_1^{10} f_4^2} (6\varphi(q^2)^2\psi(q^4) + 8q\psi(q^4)^3) \tag{90}$$

$$= \frac{f_2^9}{f_1^{10} f_4^2} \left(6 \frac{f_4^{10}}{f_2^4 f_8^4} \frac{f_8^2}{f_4} + 8q \frac{f_8^6}{f_2^3} \right) \tag{91}$$

$$\equiv 6 \frac{f_2^5 f_4^7}{f_1^{10} f_8^2} \tag{92}$$

$$= 6 \left(\frac{f_4^2}{f_1^8} \right) \frac{f_2^5 f_4}{f_1^2} \left(\frac{f_4^4}{f_8^2} \right) \tag{93}$$

$$\equiv 6 \frac{f_2^5 f_4}{f_1^2}. \tag{94}$$

Applying (42) in (94) yields

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(8n+4)q^n \equiv 6f_4 \left(\frac{f_8^5}{f_{16}^2} + 2q \frac{f_4^2 f_{16}^2}{f_8} \right) \pmod{8}. \tag{95}$$

Extracting the terms containing q^{4n} and q^{4n+1} , respectively, we have, modulo 8,

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(32n+4)q^n \equiv 6 \frac{f_1 f_2^5}{f_4^2} = 6f_1 \varphi(-q^2)^2 f(-q^2), \tag{96}$$

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(32n+12)q^n \equiv 4 \frac{f_1^3 f_4^2}{f_2} = 4f_1 \psi(q^2) f(-q)^2. \tag{97}$$

This completes the proofs of (27) and (28).

Applying the congruences $f_1^4 \equiv f_2^2 \pmod{4}$ and $f_8^2 \equiv f_4^4 \pmod{4}$ in (18) yield

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(4n+1)q^n = 2 \frac{f_4^7}{f_1^4 f_2 f_8^2} \tag{98}$$

$$= 2 \left(\frac{f_2^2}{f_1^4} \right) \frac{f_4^3}{f_2^3} \left(\frac{f_4^4}{f_8^2} \right) \tag{99}$$

$$\equiv 2 \frac{f_4^3}{f_2^3} \pmod{8}. \tag{100}$$

Extracting the terms containing q^{2n} , we obtain, modulo 8,

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(8n+1)q^n \equiv 2 \frac{f_2^3}{f_1^3} = 2 \frac{\psi(q)}{\varphi(-q)}. \tag{101}$$

Now, (43) and (47) yield

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\psi(q)}{\varphi(-q)} &= \frac{\varphi(-q^9)}{\varphi(-q^3)^4} (\Pi(q^3) + 2q\psi(q^9)) (\varphi(-q^9)^2 + 2q\varphi(-q^9)\Omega(-q^3) + 4q^2\Omega(-q^3)^2) \\ &= \frac{\varphi(-q^9)^3}{\varphi(-q^3)^4} \Pi(q^3) + 3q \frac{\varphi(-q^9)^3}{\varphi(-q^3)^4} \psi(q^9) + 6q^2 \frac{\varphi(-q^9)^2}{\varphi(-q^3)^4} \Omega(-q^3) \psi(q^9) \\ &\quad + 4q^3 \frac{\phi(-q^9)}{\phi(-q^3)^4} \Omega(-q^3)^2 \psi(q^9). \end{aligned} \tag{102}$$

From (101) and (102), and then extracting the terms containing q^{3n+i} for $i = 0, 1, 2$,

respectively, we find, modulo 8,

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(24n + 1)q^n \equiv 2 \frac{\varphi(-q^3)^3}{\varphi(-q)^4} \Pi(q) = 2 \frac{f_2^5 f_3^8}{f_1^9 f_6^4} = 2 \left(\frac{f_2^4}{f_1^8} \right) \frac{f_2}{f_1} \left(\frac{f_3^8}{f_6^4} \right) \equiv 2 \frac{f_2}{f_1}, \quad (103)$$

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(24n + 9)q^n = 6 \frac{\varphi(-q^3)^3}{\varphi(-q)^4} \psi(q^3) = 6 \frac{f_2^4 f_3^5}{f_1^8 f_6} \equiv 6 \left(\frac{f_2^4}{f_1^8} \right) f_3 f_6 \left(\frac{f_3^4}{f_6^2} \right) = 6 f_3 f_6, \quad (104)$$

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(24n + 17)q^n = 12 \frac{\varphi(-q^3)^2}{\varphi(-q)^4} \Omega(-q) \psi(q^3) \equiv 4 \left(\frac{f_2^4}{f_1^8} \right) \frac{f_1 f_3^2 f_6^2}{f_2} \equiv 4 \frac{f_1 f_3^2 f_6^2}{f_2}. \quad (105)$$

This completes the proofs of (29) and (30). Extracting the terms containing q^{3n} from (104) and using (7), we readily obtain (31). This complete the proof of Theorem 2. $\square$

If we extract the terms containing q^{3n+1} and q^{3n+2} from (104), the following two Ramanujan-like congruences can readily be obtained.

Corollary 1. *For any $n \geq 0$,*

$$\bar{p}_o(72n + 33) \equiv 0 \pmod{8}, \quad (106)$$

$$\bar{p}_o(72n + 57) \equiv 0 \pmod{8}. \quad (107)$$

We now prove Theorem 3.

Proof of Theorem 3. Extracting the terms containing q^{4n+2} and q^{4n+3} from (95), we have

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(32n + 20)q^n \equiv 0 \pmod{8}, \quad (108)$$

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(32n + 28)q^n \equiv 0 \pmod{8}. \quad (109)$$

From [11, Corollary 2.10], we have that $\bar{p}_o(2n) \equiv 0 \pmod{8}$ if $\bar{p}_o(n) \equiv 0 \pmod{8}$. This proves (32) and (33) for any $\alpha \geq 0$. $\square$

4. Infinite Families of Congruences for $\bar{p}_o(n)$

In this section, we prove Theorem 4. Before we prove Theorem 4, we first prove the following result.

Theorem 5. *Let $p \geq 3$ be a prime such that $\left(\frac{-2}{p}\right) = -1$. Then, for all nonnegative integers n and α , we have*

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(8p^{2\alpha}n + 3p^{2\alpha})q^n \equiv 4f(-q^2)^3\psi(q) \pmod{16}. \tag{110}$$

Proof. From (24), we have that (110) is true for $\alpha = 0$. We now use induction on α to complete the proof. Observe that (110) can also be written as

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o \left(8 \left(p^{2\alpha}n + 3\frac{p^{2\alpha} - 1}{8} \right) + 3 \right) q^n \equiv 4f(-q^2)^3\psi(q) \pmod{16}. \tag{111}$$

We suppose that (111) holds for some $\alpha > 0$. Substituting (49) and (52) into (111), we have, modulo 16

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o \left(8 \left(p^{2\alpha}n + 3\frac{p^{2\alpha} - 1}{8} \right) + 3 \right) q^n \tag{112} \\ & \equiv 4 \left[\frac{1}{2} \sum_{\substack{k=0 \\ k \neq \frac{p-1}{2}}}^{p-1} (-1)^k q^{k^2+k} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} (-1)^n (2pn + 2k + 1) q^{pn(pn+2k+1)} \right. \\ & \quad \left. + (-1)^{\frac{p-1}{2}} pq^{\frac{p^2-1}{4}} f(-q^{2p^2})^3 \right] \\ & \times \left[\sum_{m=0}^{\frac{p-3}{2}} q^{\frac{m^2+m}{2}} f\left(\frac{p^2 + (2m+1)p}{2}, \frac{p^2 - (2m+1)p}{2}\right) + q^{\frac{p^2-1}{8}} \psi(q^{p^2}) \right]. \end{aligned}$$

For a prime $p \geq 3$ and $0 \leq k \leq p - 1$, $0 \leq m \leq \frac{p-1}{2}$, we consider

$$(k^2 + k) + \frac{m^2 + m}{2} \equiv 3\frac{p^2 - 1}{8} \pmod{p} \tag{113}$$

which is equivalent to

$$2(2k + 1)^2 + (2m + 1)^2 \equiv 0 \pmod{p}.$$

Since $\left(\frac{-2}{p}\right) = -1$, we have $k = m = \frac{p-1}{2}$ is the only solution of (113). Therefore, extracting the terms containing $q^{pn+3\frac{(p^2-1)}{8}}$ from both sides of (112), and then replacing q^p by q , we deduce that

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o \left(8 \left(p^{2\alpha+1}n + 3\frac{p^{2\alpha+2} - 1}{8} \right) + 3 \right) q^n \equiv 4f(-q^{2p})^3\psi(q^p) \pmod{16}. \tag{114}$$

Similarly, extracting the terms containing q^{pn} from both sides of (114), and then replacing q^p by q , we obtain

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o \left(8 \left(p^{2(\alpha+1)} n + 3 \frac{p^{2(\alpha+1)} - 1}{8} \right) + 3 \right) q^n \equiv 4f(-q^2)^3 \psi(q) \pmod{16}, \tag{115}$$

proving the result for $\alpha + 1$. This completes the proof of the theorem. $\square$

Proofs of (34) and (35). From (114), it follows that

$$\bar{p}_o(8p^{2\alpha+1}(pn + j) + 3p^{2\alpha+2}) \equiv 0 \pmod{16}, \tag{116}$$

where $j = 1, 2, \dots, p - 1$. This completes the proof of (34) for $\alpha \geq 1$.

The proof of (35) proceeds along similar lines to the proof of (34). Therefore, we omit the details for reasons of brevity. $\square$

We now prove two results which will be used to prove (36) and (37).

Theorem 6. *Let $p \geq 3$ be a prime such that $\left(\frac{-2}{p}\right) = -1$. Then, for all nonnegative integers n and α , we have*

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(72p^{2\alpha}n + 9p^{2\alpha})q^n \equiv 6f(-q)f(-q^2) \pmod{8}. \tag{117}$$

Proof. Clearly, (117) is true when $\alpha = 0$ due to (31). We now use induction on α to complete the proof.

For a prime $p \geq 5$ and $-\frac{p-1}{2} \leq k, m \leq \frac{p-1}{2}$, we consider the congruence

$$\frac{3k^2 + k}{2} + 2\frac{3m^2 + m}{2} \equiv 3\frac{p^2 - 1}{24} \pmod{p}, \tag{118}$$

which is equivalent to

$$(6k + 1)^2 + 2(6m + 1)^2 \equiv 0 \pmod{p}. \tag{119}$$

Since $\left(\frac{-2}{p}\right) = -1$, therefore $k = m = \frac{\pm p-1}{6}$ is the only solution of (118). By Lemma 6 and proceeding similarly as shown in the proof of Theorem 4, we deduce the following congruence

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o \left(72 \left(p^{2\alpha+1} n + 9 \frac{p^{2\alpha+2} - 1}{72} \right) + 9 \right) q^n \equiv 6f(-q^p)f(-q^{2p}) \pmod{8}. \tag{120}$$

We next extract the terms containing q^{pn} from both sides of the above congruence, and observe that (117) is true when α is replaced by $\alpha + 1$. This completes the proof of the result. $\square$

Theorem 7. *Let $p \geq 3$ be a prime such that $\left(\frac{-2}{p}\right) = -1$. Then, for all nonnegative integers n and α , we have*

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o \left(24 \left(p^{2\alpha} n + 17 \frac{p^{2\alpha} - 1}{24} \right) + 17 \right) q^n \equiv 4f(-q^3)^3 \Omega(-q) \pmod{8}. \quad (121)$$

Proof. From (30) we can see that (121) is true when $\alpha = 0$. Suppose that (121) holds for some $\alpha > 0$. Substituting (52) and (54) into (121), we have, modulo 8

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o \left(24 \left(p^{2\alpha} n + 17 \frac{p^{2\alpha} - 1}{24} \right) + 17 \right) q^n \\ &= \left[\frac{1}{2} \sum_{\substack{m=0 \\ m \neq \frac{p-1}{2}}}^{p-1} (-1)^m q^{3 \frac{m^2+m}{2}} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} (-1)^n (2pn + 2m + 1) q^{\frac{3pn(pn+2m+1)}{2}} \right. \\ & \quad \left. + (-1)^{\frac{p-1}{2}} p q^{3 \frac{p^2-1}{8}} f(-q^{3p^2})^3 \right] \\ & \quad \times \left[\sum_{\substack{k=-\frac{p-1}{2} \\ k \neq \pm \frac{p+1}{3}}}^{\frac{p-1}{2}} (-1)^k q^{3k^2-2k} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} (-1)^n q^{pn(3pn+6k-2)} + (-1)^{\frac{\pm p+1}{3}} q^{\frac{p^2-1}{3}} \Omega(-q^{p^2}) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (122)$$

For a prime $p \geq 5$, $0 \leq m \leq p - 1$ and $-\frac{p-1}{2} \leq k \leq \frac{p-1}{2}$, we consider

$$\frac{3m(m+1)}{2} + 3k^2 - 2k \equiv 17 \frac{p^2 - 1}{24} \pmod{p}, \quad (123)$$

which is equivalent to $(6m + 3)^2 + 2(6k - 2)^2 \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$. Since $\left(\frac{-2}{p}\right) = -1$, we have $m = \frac{p-1}{2}$ and $k = \frac{\pm p+1}{3}$ is the only solution of (123). Therefore, extracting the terms containing $q^{pn+17 \frac{p^2-1}{24}}$ from both sides of (122), and then replacing q^p by q , we deduce that

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o \left(24 \left(p^{2\alpha+1} n + 17 \frac{p^{2\alpha+2} - 1}{24} \right) + 17 \right) q^n \equiv 4f(-q^{3p})^3 \Omega(-q^p) \pmod{8}. \quad (124)$$

Similarly, extracting the terms containing q^{pn} from both sides of (124), and then replacing q^p by q , we obtain

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o \left(24 \left(p^{2(\alpha+1)} n + 17 \frac{p^{2(\alpha+1)} - 1}{24} \right) + 17 \right) q^n \equiv 4f(-q^3)^3 \Omega(-q) \pmod{8}. \quad (125)$$

This completes the proof of the result. $\square$

Proofs of (36) and (37). By extracting the terms containing q^{pn+j} from (120), where $j = 1, 2, \dots, p - 1$, it follows that

$$\bar{p}_o (72p^{2\alpha}n + (9p + 72j)p^{2\alpha-1}) \equiv 0 \pmod{8}. \tag{126}$$

This completes the proof of (36) for $\alpha \geq 1$.

From (124), it follows that

$$\bar{p}_o(24p^{2\alpha+1}(pn + j) + 17p^{2\alpha+2}) \equiv 0 \pmod{8}, \tag{127}$$

where $j = 1, 2, \dots, p - 1$. This completes the proof of (37) for $\alpha \geq 1$. □

Proofs of (38) and (39). We now substitute the p -dissection identities, namely (50), (51) and (53) into (27) and (28). For $p \geq 3$, $-\frac{p-1}{2} \leq k, m \leq \frac{p-1}{2}$ and $\left(\frac{-2}{p}\right) = -1$, the congruences

$$\frac{3k^2 + k}{2} + 3m^2 + m \equiv 3\frac{p^2 - 1}{24} \pmod{p}, \tag{128}$$

$$\frac{3k^2 + k}{2} + 3m^2 + 2m \equiv 9\frac{p^2 - 1}{24} \pmod{p} \tag{129}$$

have only the solutions $k = m = \frac{\pm p-1}{6}$, and $k = \frac{\pm p-1}{6}$, $m = \frac{\pm p-1}{3}$, respectively. Proceeding similarly as shown in the proof of (37), we obtain

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o \left(32 \left(p^{2\alpha+1}n + 3\frac{p^{2\alpha+2} - 1}{24} \right) + 4 \right) q^n \equiv 6\frac{f_p f_{2p}^5}{f_{4p}^2} \pmod{8}, \tag{130}$$

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o \left(32 \left(p^{2\alpha+1}n + 9\frac{p^{2\alpha+2} - 1}{24} \right) + 12 \right) q^n \equiv 4\frac{f_p^3 f_{4p}^2}{f_{2p}} \pmod{8}. \tag{131}$$

Now, from (130) and (131), it follows that

$$\bar{p}_o(32p^{2\alpha+1}(pn + j) + 4p^{2\alpha+2}) \equiv 0 \pmod{8}, \tag{132}$$

$$\bar{p}_o(32p^{2\alpha+1}(pn + j) + 12p^{2\alpha+2}) \equiv 0 \pmod{8}, \tag{133}$$

where $j = 1, 2, \dots, p - 1$. This completes the proofs of (38) and (39) for $\alpha \geq 1$. □

Before we prove (40), we first prove the following result.

Theorem 8. *Let $p \geq 3$ be a prime such that $p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$. Then, for all nonnegative integers n and α , we have*

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o \left(16 \left(p^{2\alpha}n + 5\frac{p^{2\alpha} - 1}{8} \right) + 10 \right) q^n \equiv 8f(-q^4)^3\psi(q) \pmod{16}. \tag{134}$$

Proof. We use induction on α to proof the theorem. Clearly, (134) is true when $\alpha = 0$ due to (26). Suppose that (134) holds for some $\alpha > 0$. For a prime $p \geq 5$ and $0 \leq k \leq p - 1, 0 \leq m \leq \frac{p-1}{2}$, the equation

$$2(k^2 + k) + \frac{m^2 + m}{2} \equiv 5\frac{p^2 - 1}{8} \pmod{p}, \tag{135}$$

which is equivalent to $4(2k + 1)^2 + (2m + 1)^2 \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$, has the only solution $k = m = \frac{p-1}{2}$ as $p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$. Applying (49) and (52) in (134), and then proceeding similarly as shown in the proof of Theorem 4, we deduce that

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o \left(16 \left(p^{2\alpha+1}n + 5\frac{p^{2\alpha+2} - 1}{8} \right) + 10 \right) q^n \equiv 4f(-q^{4p})^3\psi(q^p) \pmod{16}. \tag{136}$$

Extracting the terms containing q^{pn} from both sides of (136), we find that

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o \left(16 \left(p^{2(\alpha+1)}n + 5\frac{p^{2(\alpha+1)} - 1}{8} \right) + 10 \right) q^n \equiv 4f(-q^4)^3\psi(q) \pmod{16}, \tag{137}$$

completing the proof of (134). □

Proof of (40). From (136), it follows that

$$\bar{p}_o(16p^{2\alpha+1}(pn + j) + 10p^{2\alpha+2}) \equiv 0 \pmod{16}, \tag{138}$$

where $j = 1, 2, \dots, p - 1$. This completes the proof of (40) for $\alpha \geq 1$. □

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